

ADAPTIVE STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT OF TRANSPORT ENTERPRISES IN THE CONTEXT OF MILITARY AND ECONOMIC CHALLENGES**Maksymov S.**

*Doctor of Philosophy (PhD),
Associate Professor of the Engineering Department,
Danube Institute,
National University «Odesa Maritime Academy», Ukraine, Izmail*

Dimoglova O.

*Doctor of Philosophy (PhD),
Associate Professor of the Engineering Department,
Danube Institute,
National University «Odesa Maritime Academy», Ukraine, Izmail*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20691178>

Abstract

In the article, the authors examine the features of adaptive strategic management of transport enterprises under conditions of military and economic challenges. The need to improve existing approaches to strategic planning is substantiated due to the high level of uncertainty in the external environment caused by the consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic, military aggression against Ukraine, destruction of transport infrastructure, and transformation of logistics supply chains. A review of theoretical approaches to strategic management is conducted, and the main problems of transport enterprises' functioning under current conditions are identified. An adaptive strategic planning mechanism is proposed, based on the principle of continuous adaptation of strategic decisions to changes in the internal and external environment. It is demonstrated that the application of adaptive strategic planning contributes to increasing the resilience of transport enterprises, ensures timely response to risks and opportunities, improves the quality of managerial decisions, and creates prerequisites for long-term competitive development. The practical value of the study lies in the possibility of implementing the proposed mechanism at maritime, inland waterway, road, and railway transport enterprises under martial law conditions and in the post-war recovery of the Ukrainian economy.

Keywords: adaptive strategic management, transport enterprises, transport industry, military challenges, economic instability, competitiveness.

Introduction. The current stage of development of Ukraine's transport industry is characterized by a high level of uncertainty, turbulence, and dynamism of the external environment. These conditions are shaped by globalization processes, increasing geopolitical tensions, digital transformation of the economy, and growing requirements for logistics systems. Taken together, these factors significantly complicate the forecasting of transport enterprises' development and increase the importance of strategic management as a tool for ensuring their resilience.

Recent years have been a period of severe challenges for transport enterprises. Initially, the COVID-19 pandemic led to a significant reduction in transportation volumes, disruption of global and regional supply chain logistics, and an increase in transaction costs. Subsequently, the full-scale military aggression of the Russian Federation against Ukraine resulted in even more profound negative consequences, including the destruction of transport infrastructure, blockage of certain transport corridors, changes in freight flow directions, increased insurance and operational risks, and a higher overall level of economic uncertainty.

Under such conditions, traditional approaches to strategic management, based on the extrapolation of stable development trends, have proven to be insufficiently effective. In modern economic theory, such approaches are increasingly considered limited, as they do not account for the high variability of the external environment and the rapid pace of changes in key influencing factors. Accordingly, there is an objective need

to transition to adaptive strategic planning models that ensure flexibility of managerial decisions, timely response to changes, and the maintenance of long-term enterprise competitiveness.

Therefore, the aim of the study is to provide theoretical substantiation and develop a mechanism of adaptive strategic planning for transport enterprises, focused on improving managerial efficiency under conditions of an unstable external environment.

Research materials and methods. Issues of strategic planning have been studied by many Ukrainian and international scholars. A significant contribution to the development of strategic management theory has been made by I. Ansoff [2], M. Porter [7], P. Drucker [4], and other researchers. In the works of these scholars, strategic planning is considered a multi-level process that combines analytical, forecasting, and managerial components, and ensures the formation of long-term competitive advantages.

In Ukrainian academic literature, the issues of strategic planning are represented by the works of V. Andrieiev [1], Z. Shershynova [8], M. Butko [3], I. Horbachova [5], S. Kulakova [6], and other researchers, who emphasize the adaptation of strategic approaches to the conditions of a transformational economy and an unstable market environment.

At the same time, the conducted analysis of academic sources and business practice has shown that most existing approaches to strategic planning are either oriented toward the macroeconomic level of man-

agement or do not take into account the sectoral specifics of the transport industry. Moreover, a significant number of models are static in nature and insufficiently adapted to conditions of high uncertainty and risk.

In this context, the development of dynamic, adaptive, and risk-oriented strategic planning mechanisms has become particularly relevant in modern conditions, as they allow integrating processes of external environment monitoring, risk assessment, and strategic decision adjustment in real time.

In this regard, I. Ansoff [2] viewed strategic planning as a formalized process of environmental analysis, formulation of strategic alternatives, and selection of an optimal enterprise development strategy, emphasizing the importance of portfolio analysis tools, in particular the product–market matrix. In contrast, M. Porter focused on building sustainable competitive advantages through the selection of basic competitive positioning strategies in the market [7].

Results and discussion. The study shows that, in practice, many enterprises mistakenly equate strategic planning with the development of business plans or separate development programs. However, in academic terms, strategic planning is a continuous cyclical process of forming, implementing, and adjusting long-term managerial decisions aimed at ensuring competitiveness, financial stability, and adaptability of the enterprise.

This is particularly relevant for the transport sector, as transport enterprises are critically dependent on external factors. Key determinants include fluctuations in transport demand, changes in route networks, instability of the fuel and energy market, geopolitical risks, regulatory changes, and increasing competitive pressure. The combination of these factors necessitates a shift toward flexible management models capable of ensuring rapid adaptation of strategic decisions.

Within the study, an adaptive strategic planning mechanism for transport enterprises has been proposed, the conceptual foundation of which is the principle of continuous adaptation of strategic decisions to changes in both external and internal environments. This approach involves the integration of strategic analysis, monitoring, forecasting, and managerial decision adjustment into a unified cyclical process.

The initial stage of the proposed mechanism involves the formation of prerequisites for strategic planning. Such prerequisites include significant changes in market conditions, fluctuations in transportation volumes, transformation of the regulatory framework, implementation of technological innovations, as well as the emergence of new risks and threats affecting enterprise performance.

The next stage involves comprehensive monitoring of enterprise activities. It includes the study of internal and external influencing factors, system analysis of operations, and identification of strategic development priorities.

Special attention within the proposed adaptive strategic planning mechanism is given to the use of

modern analytical tools that ensure a comprehensive analysis of the internal and external environment of the enterprise, as well as the formation of well-founded managerial decisions.

SWOT analysis is a basic strategic analysis tool that involves the identification and systematization of internal strengths and weaknesses of the enterprise, as well as external opportunities and threats. Its application allows determining the strategic position of the enterprise in the market, formulating development directions, and ensuring alignment between internal resources and external environmental requirements.

PEST analysis is used to assess the macro-environment of enterprise functioning through the examination of Political, Economic, Social, and Technological factors. This tool enables the identification of systemic trends and external determinants shaping the conditions of transport enterprises' activity, including regulatory changes, economic conditions, demographic processes, and technological innovations.

Scenario planning is a strategic forecasting method based on the construction of alternative scenarios of external environment development. It allows for the consideration of a high level of uncertainty by forming several possible trajectories of development events (optimistic, baseline, and crisis scenarios), thereby enhancing the adaptability of managerial decisions.

Matrix methods of strategic analysis (in particular the BCG matrix, GE/McKinsey matrix, and Ansoff matrix) are applied to evaluate the enterprise's business portfolio, determine priority development directions, and optimize resource allocation. They enable the classification of business units according to criteria of market attractiveness and competitive position.

Forecasting and modeling methods include a set of quantitative and qualitative approaches to predicting future values of key performance indicators of the enterprise. These include econometric modeling, simulation models, and trend models, which allow assessing possible outcomes of managerial decisions under different operating conditions.

Expert assessment methods are based on engaging industry specialists to form generalized judgments regarding market trends, risk levels, and the effectiveness of strategic alternatives. This method is particularly important under conditions of high uncertainty, when quantitative data are limited or insufficiently reliable.

Correlation and regression analysis is used to identify and quantitatively assess relationships between economic indicators of enterprise performance. It allows determining the degree of influence of individual factors on performance indicators, as well as constructing dependency models for further forecasting.

Trend extrapolation involves projecting identified historical patterns into future periods. This method is based on the assumption of relative stability of key development trends and is used for short- and medium-term forecasting of key performance indicators of the enterprise.

Fig. 1 – Block diagram of comprehensive monitoring and analytical tools for strategic management of a transport enterprise

The integrated use of the aforementioned methods enables the acquisition of more objective information regarding the current state of the enterprise and the prospects of its development.

One of the key features of the proposed mechanism is the use of a dual-term approach to strategic planning. Its essence lies in the combination of medium-term and long-term strategic plans. The medium-term plan is focused on achieving specific quantitative indicators in the near-term perspective, whereas the long-term plan defines the strategic development guidelines of the enterprise over an extended period.

Such an approach ensures a balance between strategic stability and operational flexibility of management. In the event of changing market conditions, the enterprise can adjust its medium-term objectives without the need for a complete revision of the long-term strategy.

In our view, an important element of the mechanism is the system of strategic indicators. It covers all key areas of transport enterprise activity, including:

- economic indicators;
- financial indicators;
- technical indicators;
- production indicators;
- environmental indicators;
- social indicators;
- human resource potential indicators.

Based on these indicators, an assessment of the effectiveness of strategic plan implementation is conducted, and decisions regarding its adjustment are made.

The principle of adaptability acquires particular importance under current conditions. The proposed mechanism предусматривает the continuous revision of forecast indicators depending on changes in influencing factors. This allows timely response to emerging risks and opportunities.

In addition to adaptability, the key principles of the mechanism's functioning include:

- systemness;
- scientific validity;
- comprehensiveness;
- flexibility;
- creativity;
- social orientation;
- continuous monitoring.

Conclusion. The implementation of the above-mentioned principles contributes to improving the quality of managerial decisions and ensures the formation of the enterprise's competitive advantages.

Thus, the practical significance of the proposed mechanism lies in the possibility of its application at enterprises operating in different transport modes, including maritime, inland waterway, road, and railway transport. Its use is particularly relevant for transport enterprises in Ukraine operating under martial law conditions and in the post-war economic recovery period.

Summarizing the results of the study, it can be concluded that adaptive strategic planning is one of the key instruments for ensuring the sustainable development of transport enterprises. The proposed mechanism enables the integration of a strategic vision of the future with the capacity for rapid response to changes in the external environment.

Further scientific research should be directed toward the development of a detailed algorithm for the formation of a transport enterprise strategic plan, as well as the creation of a system of quantitative indicators for assessing the effectiveness of adaptive strategic management.

References:

1. Andrieiev, V. M. (2017). Strategic planning of enterprise development in a turbulent environment. *Ekonomichnyi Prostir*, (124), 45–54.
2. Ansoff, H. I. (1965). *Corporate strategy: An analytic approach to business policy for growth and expansion*. McGraw-Hill.
3. Butko, M. P. (2016). *Stratehichnyi menedzhment* [Strategic management]. Tsentr uchbovoi literatury.
4. Drucker, P. F. (2008). *Management: Tasks, responsibilities, practices*. HarperBusiness. (Original work published 1973).
5. Horbachova, I. V. (2018). Strategic planning as a tool for enterprise development management. *Efektivna Ekonomika*, (11), 1–8.
6. Kulakova, S. Yu. (2020). Strategic planning in the system of enterprise management under conditions of economic instability. *Ekonomika ta Derzhava*, (10), 82–87.
7. Porter, M. E. (1996). What is strategy? *Harvard Business Review*, 74(6), 61–78.
8. Shershnova, Z. Ye. (2004). *Stratehichne upravlinnia* [Strategic management] (2nd ed.). KNEU.